

2 Calculation and Simulation of a Radar Antenna with Reflector 3 and a $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ Pattern Beam

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17 **Abstract:** This study presents a new approach for generating the symmetrical plan curve of a
18 double curved antenna reflector's radiation pattern, as an alternative to optimise it when the
19 primary radiation source has a given pattern. The results obtained are compared with those
20 achieved using a source with a different characteristic, clearly indicating the potential to minimize
21 the reflector surface area through illumination with a specific characteristic. Moreover, here are
22 presented the diffraction calculations for an antenna including a reflector that employs the
23 calculated vertical profile derived from a primary radiation source characterized by a given beam
24 pattern. This analysis takes into consideration two cases: one with horizontal polarization and
25 another with vertical polarization. Simulation results are provided for the diffraction calculation of
26 a reflector with radiation characteristic, that employs a sectorial horn antenna with directivity
27 characteristics. In this setup, the angular limits of the reflected beam are sequentially adjusted,
28 allowing to observe and discuss the changes in the directivity characteristic, to determine the
29 optimal configuration for the intended application.

30 **Keywords:** cosec^2 , double curved reflector, radar antenna, $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$, \cos^4

32 1. Introduction

33 Reflector antennas are widely used in communication systems for their capacity to
34 focus and direct electromagnetic waves. This paper presents in detail the diffraction
35 calculation for an antenna reflector with double curvature designed to achieve a
36 $\text{cosec}^2 \cos$ directivity characteristic, which is a variant of the optimized cosec^2
37 characteristic. The main purpose is to reduce the power level transmitted in the vicinity
38 of the radiation direction angle θ_1 , i.e. the region near the dead cone, in comparison to
39 the characteristic obtained experimentally with cosec^2 , where a significant secondary
40 lobe is observed. This characteristic is highly useful for aircraft-mounted radars
41 (scanning ground or maritime targets— the characteristic is inverted), where the lobe
42 near the dead cone zone can create disruptive signals that may jeopardize the signal
43 processing. It is also valuable for airborne surveillance radars, where reducing this lobe
44 in the dead cone zone offers a better distribution of radiated power in the directivity
45 characteristic.

46 The purpose of the article is to present in detail the method used to determine the
47 curvature in the reflector plane of symmetry that can achieve an electric field
48 distribution so that the power directivity characteristic is $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$. The main objective

49 of the paper is to elaborate a method that generates the symmetry plane curve for a
50 double curved parabolic reflector, illuminated with a horn-type primary radiation
51 source with a \cos^4 radiation characteristic in the E plane, resulting an overall directivity
52 characteristic $\operatorname{cosec}^2\cos$ in the elevation plane. A secondary objective is to model the
53 horn antenna and to simulate its radiation characteristic using the finite elements
54 methods based on Ansys HFSS, such that the overall characteristic is the desired \cos^4
55 one. Finally, a third objective is to elaborate a method to calculate the diffraction
56 characteristic of the designed antenna that has the double curved reflector with
57 $\operatorname{cosec}^2\cos$ radiation characteristic, illuminated with a horn antenna with a \cos^4
58 characteristic in the E plane. For modelling and simulation, a program has been
59 developed, that calculates the diffraction and presents the electrical field distribution in
60 the elevation plane, depending on the position vectors of the point on the reflecting
61 surface and on the angles of illumination and reflection as input data. As conclusions,
62 we highlighted the influence of those parameters on the distribution of the electrical
63 field in the elevation angle as well as the possibility of selecting the best pairs of input
64 data to achieve the best orientation for low, medium and high-altitude radars. The
65 results are highlighted in the final section.

66 The cosec^2 directivity characteristic antennas are very good for detecting and
67 tracking isolated isotropic targets that evolve at constant height, being used for military
68 or civil air surveillance radars. It worth mentioning that, for the cosec^2 characteristic,
69 there is an increased power level in the area close to the maximum angle in elevation,
70 before the dead cone area, where the dead cone represents the area where there is no
71 radiation. The $\operatorname{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ characteristic represents the optimal experimental
72 approximation for the cosec^2 characteristic, since it importantly reduces the increased
73 power level in the area close to the maximum angle in elevation, before the dead cone
74 area, and achieves a better distribution of power in elevation. Antennas with the $\operatorname{cosec}^2 \cdot$
75 \cos characteristic are useful for applications like military or civil air surveillance radars,
76 for radars installed on military or civil aircraft that have to scan the ground or sea
77 surface and for land or naval targets since they also have to reduce the clutter level in
78 the area close to the dead cone.

79 Additionally, the method used is discussed and the corresponding deduction of the
80 formulas for calculating the radiated electric field for horizontal and vertical polarization.
81 Simulations were performed using a program developed by the authors to highlight the
82 effects and importance of modifying the maximum reflection angle and minimum
83 reflection angle in shaping the directivity characteristic, as well as the variations in the
84 angle of maximum radiation direction. These simulations provide the necessary data for
85 choosing the optimal variant based on the altitude of interest for target detection and
86 tracking. This type of antenna is also suitable for integration into both military and
87 civilian radar systems operating in the 11–28 GHz frequency range, particularly those
88 intended for drone detection and tracking, where high angular resolution and directivity
89 are essential. Furthermore, it can be employed in 5G communication systems that
90 require a uniform power distribution across the antenna's radiation pattern.

91 Many researchers have studied, simulated, and attempted to implement antennas
92 targeting some important features, such as the shape of the elevation directivity
93 characteristic, the azimuth directivity characteristic opening at -3 dB, the secondary lobe
94 levels, that has to be as low as possible, the gain for each frequency, the dead cone angle
95 or maximum elevation opening, the secondary lobe shape in elevation, and the phase
96 characteristic in elevation and azimuth. Thus, in [1] is presented a study of a reflector
97 antenna developed to achieve a wide beam using a cosecant-squared pattern, for
98 communications applications with specific coverage requirements. This research delves
99 into the theoretical aspects of the antenna design, simulation results, and practical
100 considerations for implementation. It, thus, contributes to the broader field of antenna
101 engineering and may have implications for improving the performance of antenna
102 communication systems with specific beamwidth and coverage needs.

103 The authors of [2] explore a methodology for synthesizing cosecant-squared
104 radiation patterns in the context of broadband-shaped reflector antennas. The design of
105 reflector antennas plays a crucial role in various communication systems, as well as in
106 achieving a specific radiation pattern that is essential for optimizing the signal coverage.
107 Thus, here is presented a novel approach for designing reflector antennas with a
108 cosecant-squared pattern, emphasizing its applicability to broadband scenarios. This
109 research involves theoretical analyses, simulation studies, and practical considerations
110 for implementing the proposed synthesis method. The outcomes of this study may
111 contribute to advancements in antenna engineering, particularly in the development of
112 broadband-shaped reflector antennas with cosecant-squared radiation patterns, catering
113 to the demands of modern communication systems.

114 In [3] the authors investigate several main issues related to cosec^2 radiation
115 patterns synthesis for linear antenna arrays. The arrays of antennas are fundamental
116 components in communication systems, thus, their radiation patterns significantly
117 impact the signal coverage. Here, the authors propose an innovative approach that uses
118 an adaptive least squares algorithm for the synthesis of cosec^2 patterns. This involves a
119 combination of theoretical modeling, algorithm development, and practical
120 implementation considerations. The research provides a method for tailoring linear
121 antenna arrays to exhibit cosec^2 radiation patterns, which can be beneficial in
122 applications requiring specific signal coverage characteristics.

123 The authors of [4] explore the design methodology of a reflector antenna with a
124 broadband cosec^2 radiation pattern. Reflectors are critical components in
125 communication systems, thus, achieving specific radiation patterns is crucial for optimal
126 signal coverage. In this study, the authors employ the Invasive Weed Optimization
127 (IWO) procedure, a nature-inspired optimization technique, to synthesize the reflector of
128 an antenna with cosec^2 characteristic that spans a broad frequency range. The research
129 involves theoretical modelling, algorithm implementation, and practical considerations
130 for the antenna design. The principal contribution of this research is the innovative
131 approach implied in achieving broadband cosecant squared radiation patterns in
132 reflector antennas, with potential applications in communication systems requiring
133 versatile signal coverage.

134 In [5] is presented a wideband printed antenna array integrated into a corner
135 reflector, aiming to achieve a cosec^2 -shaped beam pattern. When dealing with antenna
136 arrays, it is important to achieve specific radiation patterns that is essential for obtaining
137 an effective signal coverage. In this research, the authors focus on the integration of
138 printed antenna elements into a corner reflector, using their collective arrangement to
139 synthesize a beam pattern with a cosecant square shape. This work involves theoretical
140 modelling, practical design considerations, and possibly optimization techniques to
141 achieve the desired wideband characteristics. This study provides insights into the
142 design of wideband antennas with unique beam patterns for applications requiring
143 versatile and effective signal coverage.

144 In [6] the authors focus on the design of a compact parabolic reflector antenna
145 intending to achieve a cosec^2 radiation pattern. In this study, the authors concentrate on
146 developing a parabolic reflector antenna with a cosec^2 radiation pattern, a pattern often
147 sought after for specific applications requiring controlled signal distribution. Their
148 research provides insights into the design of compact parabolic reflector antennas with
149 cosec^2 radiation patterns, tailoring to the demands of modern communication systems.

150 The authors of [7] explore the characteristics of a double-curved antenna reflector,
151 focusing on the curvature generated in the plane of symmetry, specifically designed to
152 exhibit a cosec^2 pattern beam. The reflector is illuminated by a cos^4 pattern beam from
153 the primary radiator. This research involves a combination of theoretical modeling,
154 antenna design considerations and analysis of the curve generated in the plane of
155 symmetry, offering insights into the complex geometry and radiation pattern of
156 double-curved reflectors, which is important for optimizing signal coverage in various
157 communication applications.

158 In [8] the authors explore the design and performances of a multimode array
159 antenna. Multimode antennas are versatile systems that can operate in multiple modes
160 or configurations, enabling flexibility in adapting to different communication
161 requirements and standards. In this research some important theoretical aspects of the
162 antenna's design, its multimode capabilities, and several potential applications are
163 highlighted, and several results related development of antennas capable of supporting
164 various modes for improved functionality and adaptability in diverse communication
165 scenarios are presented.

166 In [9] is presented and discussed the conception and deployment of an innovative
167 antenna array system suitable for radar applications. This research aims to address the
168 need for a versatile antenna array capable of adapting to different radar system
169 requirements. The proposed antenna array leverages a reconfigurable design that
170 combines the characteristics of a cosec^2 pattern with pencil beam focusing. This
171 configuration allows enhanced performances in radar systems, particularly in terms of
172 target detection and tracking capabilities. Key aspects of the research include the
173 methodology for designing the antenna array, which involves optimizing the geometry
174 and reconfiguration mechanisms to achieve the desired radiation pattern. The authors
175 also present some practical implementation of the antenna array and evaluate their
176 performance through simulations and experimental testing.

177 In [10] the authors focus on developing an antenna system that uses a
178 cosec^2 radiation pattern, which is beneficial for radar and communication applications.
179 Their study integrates this radiation pattern with an all-metal filter antenna design to
180 enhance its performance and efficiency. The primary focus of the research involves the
181 implementation and optimization of the antenna structure to attain the targeted cosec^2
182 pattern. Additionally, the authors investigate the practical implementation of the
183 antenna and evaluate its performance based on simulations and experimental testing.
184 Thus, this article offers valuable insights into the development of a cosec^2 pattern
185 antenna using an all-metal filter antenna, highlighting its potential utilization into
186 wireless communication networks and radar systems.

187 The authors of [11] present a study focusing on the development of a leaky wave
188 slot array antenna that uses gap waveguide technology. Their research aims to address
189 the needs of the 5G base transceiver station (BTS) applications by designing an antenna
190 with a cosec^2 radiation pattern. The primary objective of the research is to use gap
191 waveguide technology in constructing the antenna array and incorporate a
192 cosec^2 pattern to meet the specific requirements of 5G BTS applications. The authors
193 explore the design methodology, optimization strategies, and practical deployment of
194 the antenna, aiming to enhance its performance and suitability for 5G communication
195 systems, underscoring innovations in antenna technology for upcoming communication
196 networks.

197 Antennas featuring a cosec^2 pattern are integral components of air-surveillance
198 radar systems. In [12] the authors discuss the synthesis of a cosec^2 pattern leaky-wave
199 antenna (LWA) using a ridge waveguide. Achieving the desired cosec^2 pattern requires
200 precise control of attenuation and phase constants along the antenna's length. This
201 control is accomplished by appropriately narrowing the slots offset and ridge profile
202 along the antenna, facilitated by optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithms
203 (GA). The implemented antenna yields a cosecant-squared pattern LWA with an
204 expansive range from 10° to 40° , low ripples (≤ 2 dB) and reduced sidelobes (≤ -18 dB).
205 Fabrication and measurement confirm the effectiveness of the design, with simulation
206 outcomes closely matching experimental results. Notably, the design achieves a
207 significant size reduction (approximately 47%) compared to prior published works.

208 In [13] the authors address the escalating risks of oil pollution in the World Ocean,
209 particularly due to offshore oil production activities, that pose significant environmental
210 and economic threats to marine ecosystems and coastal regions. To effectively monitor
211 water surfaces and detect oil spills, modern and reliable remote monitoring methods are
212 essential, with radar being a prominent option. This study focuses on enhancing the

213 radar method's efficiency for water surface monitoring through constructive
214 modifications of the existing radar antenna array and alterations of the radio signal's
215 shape. In this paper is presented in depth theoretical radar analysis and mathematical
216 modelling, justifying the efficacy of using a phased active antenna array and
217 constructing a cosec^2 pattern diagram for the radio signal. This approach aims to
218 improve radar monitoring efficiency, facilitating quicker and more accurate detection of
219 oil spills, thereby aiding in timely intervention and mitigation efforts.

220 The authors of [14] explore the design of reflector antennas across various
221 frequencies by employing frequency selective surfaces (FSS). Reflector antennas are
222 essential components in wireless communication systems, serving to direct and focus
223 electromagnetic signals. Frequency selective surfaces are used in this study to tailor the
224 antenna's performance at specific frequencies, enhancing its efficiency and functionality.
225 Based on the theoretical analysis and practical experimentation presented in this paper
226 the authors investigate the application of FSS in optimizing reflector antenna designs
227 across different frequency bands. By manipulating the properties of FSS, such as their
228 periodicity and geometry, several performance characteristics of the antenna, such as
229 gain, directivity, and bandwidth, can be tailored to meet specific requirements. This
230 approach allows the improvement of the performance of communication systems
231 operating in diverse frequency bands, thereby facilitating enhanced connectivity and
232 communication capabilities in wireless networks.

233 The research presented in [15] details the development of a multi-purpose aperture
234 antenna suitable for operation at both L and S-bands, specifically designed for use in
235 airborne synthetic aperture radar (SAR) systems. It has been imposed to ensure
236 consistent beamwidth along the aircraft's route in both frequency bands. It utilizes a
237 probe-fed square annular patch antenna for L-band and an electromagnetically coupled
238 stacked patch antenna for S-band, set up in arrays of 2×6 and 2×12 elements respectively,
239 all on the same aperture measuring 0.35×1.2 m. The antenna proved to achieve a 200
240 MHz bandwidth at L-band, respectively 400 MHz at S-band, a peak gain of 6.3 dBi at
241 1.25 GHz, respectively 19 dBi at 3.2GHz and more than 30dB port isolation and
242 cross-polarization at both frequencies.

243 In [16] a pattern synthesis method for a planar array of isotropic antennas using a
244 Genetic Algorithm (GA) is presented. The study concentrates on creating two separate
245 beam patterns: a pencil beam pattern and an omnidirectional pattern. The GA is utilized
246 to identify the best combination of element amplitudes and phases to achieve reduced
247 Peak Side Lobe Level (PSLL) and ripple. These optimized excitations, derived through
248 GA, provide discrete solutions that help in decreasing the Dynamic Range Ratio (DRR).
249 A lower DRR not only assists in simplifying design complexity but also enhances the
250 performance of the feed network.

251 The authors of [17] discuss polarimetric radars and polarization antennas. In the
252 context of a frequency-modulated millimetre-wave (FMCW) radar system, the authors
253 presented a new dual-polarization antenna design that they believed would be suitable
254 for both single-input single-output (SISO) and input multiple output (SIMO) at 24 GHz.
255 Angular target tracking and range estimation is achieved by using four possible
256 transmitter and receiver polarization combinations, namely horizontal-horizontal (H-H),
257 horizontal-vertical (H-V), vertical-horizontal (V-H) and vertical-vertical (V-V). It is noted
258 that the basic radar antenna is well matched from about 23.3 GHz to 25.5 GHz with
259 isolation exceeding 35dB.

260 In [18] a microstrip antenna design is suitable for use in short-range radar studies
261 because it has an E-shaped array and reflector is presented, that is shown to achieve a
262 high gain. The antenna proposed by the authors presents gains of 7.85 and 9.62 dBi at
263 resonance frequencies of 1.4 and 2.4 GHz and, in addition, features an
264 forward-backward (F/B) ratio exceeding 15 dB and a width of the beam where the
265 radiated power falls to 50% suitable for short-range applications.

266 The authors of [19] propose an antenna that operates at 0.5 GHz, intended for use in
267 ground penetrating radar (GPR) applications with good performances at low

268 frequencies. The design incorporates an improved rectangular reflector with enhanced
 269 antenna gain and directivity. The performances have been evaluated based on the
 270 radiation pattern, the gain achieved and the return loss. Two cases were considered, one
 271 using a reflector and one without the reflector. The results shown better results with the
 272 reflector, with a large bandwidth (0.4 GHz - 1.25 GHz) and an increased gain (0.4 GHz -
 273 1.25 GHz) In [20] the authors present propose a novel method combining a pre-selection
 274 strategy with a multi-level dynamic thresholding mechanism to improve both accuracy
 275 and efficiency for massive MIMO systems.

276 However, none of the studies presented above do not extend in extenso the
 277 theoretical evaluation of the specific $\text{cosec}^2 \cos$ characteristic, its radiation characteristic
 278 and its performances in terms of electrical field distribution depending on the
 279 illumination and elevation angles. They have been only marginally mentioned in [25],
 280 where several of their advantages have been mentioned, without any demonstration or
 281 performance evaluation. By presenting our results we consider that we are closing the
 282 knowledge gap related to those antennas.

283 The reminder of the paper is organized as follows: in Section 2, details about double
 284 curved antenna reflectors are presented, and the relations used to obtain the ideal
 285 cosec^2 elevation characteristic are highlighted. In Section 3, calculations are presented
 286 using optical geometric methods for the characteristic in the vertical plane, as well as for
 287 the characteristic in the vertical plane when using a primary radiator with \cos^4
 288 directivity. In Section 4, the results obtained from the simulations conducted are
 289 presented, along with the main conclusions.
 290

291 2. Reflector for Double Curved Antennas

292 The double-curved reflector constitutes a standard component in various search
 293 and tracking radar antenna systems. Initially designed to fulfil the operational demands
 294 of search radars, it offers an extended elevation range while maintaining the precise
 295 bearing resolution typical of parabolic reflector antennas.

296 This type of reflector illuminated by a primary radiation source with an appropriate
 297 directive function emerged when the requirements for the detection and observation of
 298 aerial targets required a wide angular range in elevation where the target could be well
 299 observed and a very good angular resolution in azimuth. For such radar stations where
 300 the detection of aerial targets must be done at different elevation angles, a narrow
 301 directive characteristic in the horizontal plane is necessary, and in the vertical plane for
 302 the elevation angle $\theta \in [\theta_1; \theta_2]$, a constant amplitude signal must be obtained at the
 303 receiver input, i.e. the power distribution on the reflector surface must be a well-known
 304 function. For the angles $\theta \notin [\theta_1; \theta_2]$, the energy distribution function on the reflector
 305 surface, $F(\theta)$, must be null i.e. the signal at the receiver input must be zero. The distance
 306 is determined by measuring the time between the echo pulse (reflected by the target)
 307 and the reference pulse (emitted by the antenna); constant power, independent of the
 308 distance value, ensures the necessary signal-to-noise ratio. These conditions are met by
 309 the elevation directivity characteristic cosec^2 . These conditions and performances for the
 310 directivity characteristic in elevation with a large angular aperture and in the azimuthal
 311 plane with a very good angular resolution and a constant power at reception, cannot be
 312 obtained with an antenna with a parabolic reflector regardless of the chosen
 313 configuration. The option of obtaining a similar characteristic with a phased array
 314 antenna is very expensive both for calibration and for operation.

315 It is known that the received power [21,23,25] varies inversely with the fourth
 316 power of the slant distance from the reflector to the target R

$$317 P_r = \frac{P_T \cdot G_T \cdot G_R \cdot \lambda^2 \cdot \sigma}{(4 \cdot \pi)^3 \cdot R^4} \quad (1)$$

318 where

$$P_r = \text{const.} \quad (2)$$

$$G_T = G_R$$

and

319 P_T – is the power of the radar radiation emitted,
 320 λ – is the wavelength of the transmitter,
 321 σ – is the effective reflection area of the target, for a target flying in a constant
 322 direction, it can be considered in a first approximation as $\sigma \approx \text{const}$.

323 $G_T = G_T(\theta)$ – is the antenna gain at transmission, for a direction with elevation
 324 angle θ

325 $G_R = G_R(\theta)$ – is the antenna gain at reception, for a direction with elevation angle
 326 θ .

327 But according to relation (2) it can be written $G_T(\theta) = G_R(\theta) = G(\theta)$

328 In Figure 1, an ideal cosec^2 elevation directive characteristic is presented, which
 329 can provide a complete picture of the relationship between the incline distance R at an
 330 angle θ and the target height, thus achieving constant power reception at any elevation
 331 angle.

332 **Figure 1.** The ideal cosec^2 elevation directive characteristic

333 If the height of the target H is constant, it can be calculated as a function of the
 334 distance from the reflector to the target R , as shown in the Figure. 1, is calculated by

335
$$R \cdot \sin \theta = H \quad (3)$$

336 resulting

337
$$R = H \cdot \text{cosec} \theta \quad (4)$$

338 The received power [22] is proportional to the gain, that is, to the power directive
 339 gain in any direction

340
$$P_r = \frac{P_T \cdot \lambda^2 \cdot \sigma \cdot G(\theta)^2}{(4 \cdot \pi)^3 \cdot H^4 \cdot \text{cosec}^4 \theta} \quad (5)$$

341 But, since

342
$$P_r = ct.; P_T = ct.; \text{ result } P_r/P_T = ct. \quad (6)$$

343 it results

344
$$G(\theta) = \frac{4 \cdot \pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{P_r}{P_T} \cdot \frac{4 \cdot \pi}{\sigma}} \cdot H^2 \text{cosec}^2 \theta = K \cdot \text{cosec}^2 \theta; \quad (7)$$

345 where:
$$K = \frac{4 \cdot \pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{P_r}{P_T} \cdot \frac{4 \cdot \pi}{\sigma}} \cdot H^2$$

346 Such characteristics can be obtained using geometric optics methods by calculating
 347 the curvature of the reflecting surface in the vertical plane. In several research [1,16,21,25]
 348 experimentally determined modified cosec^2 directive characteristics have been used for
 airborne radars

349
$$G(\theta) = K \cdot \text{cosec}^2 \theta \cdot \cos \theta \quad (8)$$

or [22,25, 27] for radar antennas placed on aircraft

$$G(\theta) = K \cdot \text{cosec}^2 \theta \cdot \sqrt{\text{ctg} \theta} \quad (9)$$

350 The cosec^2 characteristic is ideal for constant altitude flight with isolated isotropic
 351 target, being commonly used in airborne target detection radars. The
 352 characteristic $G(\theta) = K \cdot \text{cosec}^2 \theta \cdot \cos \theta$ represents the optimal [22,25] experimental

approximation for the cosec^2 characteristic for antennas designed to operate at wavelengths of 1 to 10 cm.

At this point it is necessary to mention that such a discontinuous energy distribution, as the one shown above, with a reflector of limited dimensions is practically impossible to achieve. Diffraction phenomena are inevitable, and what can be hoped for, at best, is to achieve a very good approximation of the optimal model for the function $F(\theta)$ in the range of angles $\theta \in [\theta_1; \theta_2]$ and with an acceptable level of field intensity outside this interval.

First and foremost, it must be noted that, for determining the azimuth of the discovered target in the horizontal plane, a symmetric directive characteristic is used, which can be formed by a reflector with a parabolic profile in the horizontal plane for the reflection directions. In this case, the horizontal profile is parabolic (for the reflection directions), while the vertical profile has a curvature obtained through numerical integration, based on the condition of achieving a cosec^2 power distribution. The primary radiation source can be a horn antenna or a slot antenna.

3. Calculus using Optical Geometric Methods

A. The characteristic in the vertical plane.

To achieve the cosec^2 pattern of radiation in the elevation plane, it's essential to create a function that represents the profile of the reflector in the vertical plane, ensuring a cosec^2 power distribution. Following the principle of energy conservation, applied specifically in the optical geometric methods used for designing the double-curved radiator, the energy of the incoming ray must equal the energy of the reflected ray.

If $f(\gamma)$ is the power emitted by the primary reflector in a unitary the solid angle, as shown in Figure.1, the power emitted by the primary reflector situated in the focal point F , in a solid angle $d\gamma \cdot d\psi$, is:

$$f(\gamma) \cdot d\gamma \cdot d\psi \quad (10)$$

After reflecting on surface Σ , it becomes a spatial sector with angular aperture $d\theta$ and width $\rho \cdot d\psi$, such as the power density of the reflected beam $F(\theta)$ fulfills the energy conservation rule, thus resulting

$$f(\gamma) \cdot d\gamma \cdot d\psi = F(\theta) \cdot d\theta \cdot \rho \cdot d\psi \quad (11)$$

or

$$f(\gamma) \cdot d\gamma = \rho \cdot F(\theta) \cdot d\theta. \quad (12)$$

Letting γ_1 and γ_2 the incident beam angular limits, their correspondents in the secondary beam are θ_1 and θ_2 , such that

$$F(\theta) \cdot d\theta = \frac{f(\gamma)}{\rho} \cdot d\gamma \cdot \int_{\theta_1}^{\theta_2} F(\theta) d\theta / \int_{\gamma_2}^{\gamma_1} \frac{f(\gamma)}{\rho} d\gamma \quad (13)$$

For solving this, we define the variable

$$s = \rho / \rho_2 \quad (14)$$

where ρ_2 is the largest value of position [21, 28, 29] vector absolute value, i.e. from focal point to the current point. We can rewrite then (13) as

$$F(\theta) \cdot d\theta = \frac{f(\gamma)}{s} \cdot d\gamma \cdot \int_{\theta_1}^{\theta_2} F(\theta) d\theta / \int_{\gamma_2}^{\gamma_1} \frac{f(\gamma)}{s} d\gamma \quad (15)$$

Since $\left| \int_{\gamma_2}^{\gamma_1} \frac{f(\gamma)}{s} d\gamma \right| < 1$, we may choose a constant $C_1 < 1$ such that

$$\int_{\gamma_2}^{\gamma_1} f(\gamma) \cdot \frac{1}{s} \cdot d\gamma = \frac{1}{C_1} \int_{\gamma_1}^{\gamma_2} f(\gamma) \cdot d\gamma \quad (16)$$

Introducing the constant σ ,

$$\sigma = \int_{\theta_1}^{\theta_2} F(\theta) d\theta / \int_{\gamma_1}^{\gamma_2} f(\gamma) d\gamma \quad (17)$$

results

$$F(\theta) \cdot d\theta = \frac{f(\gamma) \cdot d\gamma}{s} \cdot \sigma \cdot C_1 \quad (18)$$

Figure 2 shows the necessary details and notations for optical calculation. To simplify the computation effort, we can make a convenient choice of the system axis, the angle measurement convention for the position vectors of the incident beam γ , with magnitude $\rho = \rho(\gamma, \theta)$. The angles of the radiation directions of the reflected beam θ , as they result from the optical calculation, are a function of the angle of the current position vector in the incident beam γ , the limits of the incident beam, and the limits of the reflected beam, namely $\theta = \theta(\gamma; \gamma_1; \gamma_2; \theta_1; \theta_2)$. The solid angle of the incident beam is suggestively depicted $d\gamma \cdot d\psi$ with the position vector ρ at an angle of incidence γ from the reference point F (where the primary radiation source is positioned) onto a very narrow surface element around the curvature Γ in the reflector's plane of symmetry. Additionally, the corresponding reflected beam for the angle of reflection θ is shown with its aperture $d\theta$ and width $\rho \cdot d\psi$.

Figure 2. Power density evaluation for the incident and reflected beams [8], [21,22]

To determine the mathematical expression of the curvature in the vertical plane, namely the instantaneous vector ρ as a function of γ and θ . Since the curve $\theta = \theta(\gamma; \gamma_1; \gamma_2; \theta_1; \theta_2)$ is defined in polar coordinates, we need to evaluate first the equation fulfilled by the tangent to the curve.

Figure 3 shows the necessary details and notations for optical calculation. To reduce the calculation effort it is necessary to make a convenient choice of the axis system, the angle measurement convention for the position vectors of the incident beam (with magnitude ρ , θ), and the angles of the radiation directions of the reflected beam θ (resulting from the optical calculation, which are a function of the angle of the current position vector in the incident beam, the limits of the incident beam, and the limits of the reflected beam).

Considering that the focus is placed on the x-axis at distance f_0 from the origin, the curve is generated in the right semi-plane, $\gamma_1 < 0, \gamma_2 > 0$, thus θ_2 is in the second quadrant and θ_1 is in the first quadrant. Therefore, the angles θ are positive, in the first quadrant with values $\theta \in (0; 70]^\circ$, as shown in Figure 3. It results

$$U_i^n = \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\theta - \gamma}{2} \quad (19)$$

where U_i^n is the angle between the incident ray and the normal to the surface.

The tangent to the curve expression [2,3,4] is given by

$$\frac{d\rho}{\rho} = -tg \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2} d\gamma \quad (20)$$

This relation is valid when the primary radiator directivity characteristic is determined empirically point-by-point and it can be approximated using Simpson 1/3 numerical integration method.

Figure 3. The axes system, incident and reflection angles [22] and the notations used for diffraction calculus

In figure 4, the angle notations and conventions are presented for the position vectors corresponding to the incident ray \vec{r}_i , the reflected ray \vec{r}_r in relation to the normal \vec{n} , and the tangent $\vec{\tau}$ to the curve in the symmetry plane at the incidence point. These notations are necessary to evaluate the relationship between the tangent angle to the curve in the plane of symmetry in the incidence point of V , the angle of incidence γ , the angle of reflection θ , and the incident, U_i^n , and reflected, U_r^n , rays angles to the characteristic in the plane of symmetry.

Figure 4. Position vector calculation [22]

B. The characteristic in the vertical plane when using a primary radiator with the directivity \cos^4

In this case, knowing the directivity characteristic of the primary reflector, we need to calculate the curve expression in the vertical plane that ensure the desired power density of the reflected beam pattern, $F(\theta)$ [15-16, 22, 27]. First, we can assume that the variation of ρ has little or no effect on the primary radiation pattern power density, thus equation (12) can be re-written as

$$f(\gamma) d\gamma = a \cdot F(\theta) d\theta \quad (21)$$

where $a = 1/\sigma$ is a constant that has to be determined such that the energy of the incident beam in between γ_1 and γ_2 is equal with the one of the reflected beam in between θ_1 and θ_2 , where σ is given by (17). The notations are pictorially presented in Figure 2.

We choose for the primary radiator the directivity function

$$f(\gamma) = \cos^4 \gamma \quad (22)$$

and a reflector with the power density

$$F(\theta) = \frac{\cos\theta}{\sin^2\theta} = \operatorname{cosec}^2\theta \cdot \cos\theta, \quad \theta \neq 0 \quad (23)$$

Then, using (17), (22) and (23) we have

$$\sigma = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sin\theta_1} - \frac{1}{\sin\theta_2}\right)}{\frac{3}{8} \cdot (\gamma_2 - \gamma_1) + \frac{\sin(2\cdot\gamma_2) - \sin(2\cdot\gamma_1)}{4} + \frac{\sin(4\cdot\gamma_2) - \sin(4\cdot\gamma_1)}{32}} \quad (24)$$

Also, integrating (21), and with (22) and (23) we obtain

$$\theta = \arcsin \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\sin(\theta_1)} - \sigma \cdot \left[\frac{3}{8} \cdot (\gamma - \gamma_1) + \frac{\sin(2\cdot\gamma) - \sin(2\cdot\gamma_1)}{4} + \frac{\sin(4\cdot\gamma) - \sin(4\cdot\gamma_1)}{32} \right]} \quad (25)$$

On the other hand, using

$$f(\gamma) = \cos^2\gamma \quad (26)$$

instead of (22) (19-21), we obtain

$$\theta = \arcsin \frac{1}{\left\{ \frac{1}{\sin(\theta_1)} - \frac{[2 \cdot (\gamma - \gamma_1) + \sin(2\gamma) - \sin(2\gamma_1)] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sin\theta_1} - \frac{1}{\sin\theta_2}\right)}{[2 \cdot (\gamma_2 - \gamma_1) + \sin(2\gamma_2) - \sin(2\gamma_1)]} \right\}} \quad (27)$$

By contrast with the general method presented in section A, where we have chosen for the position vector its maximum absolute value, ρ_2 , we may choose a known value for the position vector, for example the position of the focus f_0 . Thus, the integral may be evaluated on sub-intervals since the position vector is known. For $\gamma_{2k} \in [\gamma_2; \pi]$, (20) becomes

$$\rho_{sk} = \exp(\ln f_0 - \int_{\gamma_{2k}}^{\pi} tg \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2} d\gamma) \quad (28)$$

and for $\gamma_{1k} \in [\pi; \gamma_1]$ it becomes

$$\rho_{ik} = \exp(\ln f_0 - \int_{\pi}^{\gamma_{1k}} tg \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2} d\gamma) \quad (29)$$

The mathematical steps used for integrating equation (20) and obtaining the curve in the symmetry plane in cartesian coordinates and reflector surfaces are described in detail in references [21, 22]

Figure 5 presents the shape of the curve in the symmetry plane when using a \cos^2 illumination and for \cos^4 illumination. The rest of the parameters, i.e. $\gamma_1; \gamma_2; \theta_1; \theta_2$ are the same. Figure 6 represents details of Figure 5, that emphasize the differences between the two characteristics.

In figure 6, details are provided to clearly highlight the differences between the two curves presented in figure 5. These differences, in the vertical plane, are significant at the top and bottom edges of the reflector. Reducing the reflector's surface provides the advantage of decreasing aerodynamic load, reducing the dimensions of the support structure, and consequently, the weight of the reflector.

In Figure 7, an example of a sectoral horn antenna with linear polarization in the E-plane is presented, which can be used to illuminate a reflector generated with the curve from the symmetry plane defined by equations (22-25), (28), and (29). The sectoral horn antenna in Figure is prepared for simulating the radiation characteristics using the finite element method on the Ansys HFSS platform. For this simulation the following setting shave been used: HFSS Driven Modal, Material: pec, Boundaries: Perfect E1/Radiation/vacuum/Radiating Only, Excitation: Wave port/Properties/General Name: 1/Modes: Number of modes1, Integration line: defined, Characteristic impedance Z0: Zpi/Mode Alignment and Polarity: Set mode polarity using integration lines

Figure 5. The characteristic in the vertical plane obtained by using (25) and the one obtained by using (26)

Figure 6. Details of Figure 5: showing segment under the x-axis (a) respectively the peak of the characteristic (b)

Figure 7. The sectoral horn antenna with linear polarization in the E-plane prepared for simulating the radiation characteristics using the finite element method on the Ansys HFSS platform

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In figures 8, 9 and 10 are shown the results of simulating the radiation characteristics for the horn antenna from figure 7. Firstly, the results obtained for the 3D radiation pattern are presented (figures 8.a-f).

Figure 8.a. The 3D radiation pattern in normalized power represented in polar coordinates

Figure 8.b. The 3D radiation pattern in normalized power represented in polar coordinates, azimuth view

Figure 8.c. The 3D radiation pattern in normalized power represented in polar coordinates, elevation view

Figure 8.d. The 3D radiation pattern in normalized power at 0dB represented in polar coordinates

Figure 8.e. The 3D radiation pattern normalized to 0dB power represented in polar coordinates, elevation view

Figure 8.f. The 3D radiation pattern normalized to 0dB power represented in polar coordinates, azimuth view

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In Figures 9.a-b, the radiation pattern in the E-plane and the radiation pattern in the H-plane i.e. the total power gain normalized to 0dB, are presented in cartesian

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coordinates as a function of the elevation angle θ , with the plane of polarization angle set to $\psi = 90^\circ$.

Figure 9.a. The radiation pattern in the E-plane

Figure 9.b. The radiation pattern in the H-plane

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In Figure 10.a, the reflector, which has a curvature in the plane of symmetry obtained using equations (22-29), is presented, from a lateral view. In Figure 10.b, the reflector, which has a curve in the symmetrical plane obtained using equations (22-29), is presented from frontal view, showing the plane of symmetry to the boundary of the opening in the horizontal plane. For the numerical computation and graphical modelling for equations (22-29) has been developed the program ANCSOCO4.PAS in Turbo-Pascal 7.0, that has been then transposed in Mathcad 2000 and Matlab.

Figure 10.a. The reflector - lateral view

Figure 10.b. The reflector - frontal view

4. Distribution of the electromagnetic field when the double-curved reflector is used.

Due to computation complexity, a closed form for the electromagnetic field cannot be determined in the general case. We'll consider a simplified approach [8,16, 10, 26, 27], in which we have a long-range illumination on the curve in the plane of symmetry of the characteristic. The electromagnetic field is determined using the Kottler formula [8,16]

$$\vec{E}_M = j \frac{e^{-jkR}}{2\lambda R} \iint [\vec{R}_1 \times (\vec{E} \times \vec{n}) + \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}} (\vec{H} \times \vec{n})_N] \cdot e^{j \cdot k \cdot \rho \cdot \cos(\alpha)} \cdot d\sigma \quad (30)$$

$$\vec{H}_M = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\mu}} (\vec{R}_1 \times \vec{E}_M) \quad (31)$$

where

R - is the distance from the origin to the point in which we evaluate the electromagnetic field (P);

\vec{R}_1 - is the unit vector of FP (from figure 12)

α - the angle between FP and FM (from figure 12)

λ - wavelength

$k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ - wave number

\vec{E}_M - the total electric field at point M

\vec{H}_M - the total magnetic field at point M

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Figure 11. The notation used for diffraction calculation

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 510 The index N shows that the vector product $(\bar{H} \times \bar{n})_N$ is projected on the normal
 511 line of the plane that includes the FP segment and vector \bar{H} . Only a narrow surface,
 512 resting on the central curve in the vertical plane of symmetry is considered, as shown in
 513 figure 11. This surface can be considered as a cylinder of very small height whose
 514 intersection with the plane (xOy) is the central curve in the vertical plane of symmetry.

515 Let F be the point where the phase centre of the primary radiation source is located.
 516 Then, it coincides with the origin O of the axes system in which the calculation of the
 517 coordinates of the vertical curve in the plane of symmetry was carried out. To simplify
 518 the calculations furthermore, the cylinder considered above will be positioned
 519 perpendicular to the (xOy) plane. The diffraction field in the direction of FP , which
 520 makes an angle with the Ox axis at point P , must be calculated. Since it is considered that
 521 P is far away, MP and FP can be considered parallel. Let also \bar{n} and $\bar{\tau}$ be the normal and
 522 the tangent in M to the central curve. We assume that the surface is illuminated by a
 523 primary source, placed in F , and the angle between \bar{n} and MF is the angle of incidence i
 524 and the incident ray FM , resulting in a reflected ray $\bar{\tau}$, following a direction generally
 525 different from MP .

526 The primary wave from F is spherical, with power density I , in the FM direction,
 527 with an angle γ with the Fz axis. As the surface is reflective, the electric field is normal,
 528 thus $(\bar{E} \times \bar{n})=0$, since, when linear polarization is used, \bar{E} is perpendicular to the (xOy)
 529 plane. Thus, the reflection introduces an electric field equal and opposite to the incident
 530 one (i.e. 180° phase shift) and therefore the total field in M is zero and from the initial
 531 formula only the second term can be considered.

532 The second case which will be studied, is the one in which the electric field of the
 533 incoming ray lies in the (xOy) plane and $(\bar{E} \times \bar{n})$ will be normal to the (xOy) plane (i.e.
 534 vertical linear polarization).

535 Figure 12 shows all the details and notations necessary for diffraction calculation.
 536 The following angles are depicted: the angle between the incident radiation direction
 537 from point F to point M (the current calculation point) and the direction vector, defined
 538 between point F and point P (with angle θ_p) in the radiation space where the field \bar{E} is
 539 calculated, denoted by α ; the angle between the direction vector defined between points
 540 M and P (parallel to FP) and the normal to the curve in the symmetry plane at point M ,
 541 denoted by μ ; and the angle i between the radiation direction from point M with

542 inclination (relative to the x-axis) θ and the normal to the curve at point M . From the
 543 figure, the angular relationships between these angles and the normal to the curve in the
 544 symmetry plane (from the surface element) can be deduced.

545
 546 *A. Electrical field evaluation for horizontal linear polarization*

547 The total electrical field in point M is zero, since, based on the properties of
 548 reflection phenomenon, it introduces an electrical field equal as amplitude to and out of
 549 phase to the incident field. On the other hand, the aggregate magnetic field in the same
 550 point, M , is tangent and has twice the value of the tangential component of the magnetic
 551 field. Assuming a spherical primary wave the incident electrical field is given by

$$E_i = e^{-jk\rho} \cdot \sqrt{f(\gamma) \cdot Z_0} / \rho \quad (32)$$

552 But in the incident beam, the magnetic field is proportional to E_i , so the magnetic
 553 field is:

$$H_i = e^{-jk\rho} \cdot \sqrt{f(\gamma) \cdot Z_0} / \rho \quad (33)$$

554 In both formulas the exponential factor $k \cdot \rho$ explains the phase delay along the
 555 direction of the ρ ray where: $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$; $f(\gamma) = \cos^4(\gamma)$; $Z_0 = \sqrt{\mu_0/\epsilon_0}$.

556 The magnetic field, \vec{H} that will be considered is $2 \cdot H_i \cdot \cos i$ because the tangential
 557 component of the incident magnetic field is $H_i \cdot \cos i$. Since \vec{H} is projected on the
 558 tangent $\vec{\tau}$ which is perpendicular to the normal \vec{n} , the modulus of the vector product is:

$$|\vec{H} \times \vec{n}| = 2H_i \cos(i) = 2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{f(\gamma) \cdot Z_0}}{\rho} \cdot e^{-jk\rho} \cdot \cos(i) \quad (34)$$

559 Since the integral (30) is determined on a very narrow area, it may be regarded as a
 560 contour integral.

$$E_\rho = j \cdot \frac{e^{-jkR}}{\lambda R} \int \frac{\sqrt{f(\gamma) \cdot Z_0}}{\rho} \cdot \cos(i) \cdot e^{-jk\rho(1-\cos\alpha)} ds \quad (35)$$

561 One can notice that:

$$\alpha = \gamma - \theta_p$$

$$i = \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2}$$

$$\frac{\rho'}{\rho} = -\operatorname{tg} \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2}$$

$$ds = \sqrt{\rho^2 + (\rho')^2} d\gamma = \rho \cdot d\gamma / \cos \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2} \quad (36)$$

562 Using (36) in (35), after algebraic manipulations, we obtain

$$E_\rho = j \cdot \frac{\sqrt{Z_0} \cdot e^{-jkR}}{\lambda R} \cdot \int_{\gamma_1}^{\gamma_2} \cos^2(\gamma) \cdot e^{-jk\rho(1-\cos(\gamma-\theta_p))} d\gamma \quad (37)$$

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 564 *B. Electrical field evaluation for vertical linear polarization*

565 The incoming magnetic field is now considered to be perpendicular to the (xOy)
 566 plane, being dictated solely by its tangential component. We therefore obtain

$$E_\rho = j \cdot \frac{e^{-jkR}}{\lambda R} \cdot \int_{\gamma_1}^{\gamma_2} \sqrt{Z_0} \cdot \cos^2(\gamma) \cdot e^{-jk\rho(1-\cos(\gamma-\theta_p))} d\gamma \quad (38)$$

567 or knowing that $\mu = \theta_p + \pi - \gamma - i$ and replacing the result is:

$$E_\rho = j \cdot \frac{\sqrt{Z_0} \cdot e^{-jkR}}{\lambda R} \int_{\gamma_1}^{\gamma_2} \cos^2(\gamma) \cdot \left[\cos(\pi + \theta_p - \gamma) + \sin(\pi + \theta_p - \gamma) \cdot \operatorname{tg} \frac{\theta + \pi - \gamma}{2} \right] \cdot e^{-jk\rho[1-\cos(\gamma-\theta_p)]} \cdot d\gamma \quad (39)$$

568 Depending on the application chosen, the directivity characteristic can be shaped as
 569 follows:

570 - by changing the reflection angle from the base of the reflector, θ_1 , which affects
 571 the dead cone angle and the lobes formed around it, as well as the power distribution in
 572 the directivity characteristic.

573 - by changing the reflection angle from the upper edge of the reflector, θ_2 , which
574 affects the change in the angle of maximum radiation direction, the dead cone angle (the
575 area between the radiation direction with angle θ_2 and the antenna's rotation axis), and
576 the lobes formed around it, as well as the power distribution in the directivity
577 characteristic, in the angular sector forming the first half of the elevation directivity
578 characteristic from the maximum radiation direction towards the dead cone. Modifying
579 the angle θ_2 makes the difference between an elevation directivity characteristic for low
580 heights and an elevation directivity characteristic for medium and high heights.

581 - by changing the angles γ_1 and γ_2 , that must be performed in correlation with the
582 modification of angles θ_1 and θ_2 so that there are no reflections at the edges of the
583 reflector and the reflected power is not significantly reduced due to the large angle
584 between the incident wave and the reflected wave. Modifying angles γ_1 and γ_2 involves
585 recalculating the primary radiation source (horn antenna).

586 - it is necessary to mention that, by changing the angles θ_1 si θ_2 we obtain, for
587 each value of the angle another curve in the symmetry plane, leading to a different
588 reflective surface, with the same elevation characteristic but different opening angles in
589 elevation, without significant change of the azimuthal parameters.

590 Using the method presented above, developed in the numerical calculation and
591 graphical modelling program DIAGCCOS.PAS in Turbo-Pascal 7.0, we performed the
592 simulation of the normalized electric field distribution at the maximum value
593 $En(\theta_P) = E\rho(\theta, \theta_p, \gamma, \rho)/Emax$ (where: $E_-(\rho)$ is given by (39), $Emax$ is the maximum
594 value of $E\rho(\theta, \theta_p, \gamma, \rho)$ and the vectors ρ and the angles θ, γ in accordance with (21-29)
595 are calculated numerically by ANCSOCO4.PAS. The DIAGCCOS.PAS program is created
596 for a double curved reflector (graphite material), with a sector horn type primary
597 radiation source with characteristic cos^4 , to obtain the characteristic $cosec^2 \cdot coscos$, for
598 a wavelength of 10.6 cm and vertical polarization.

599 In figures 12-16 are presented the simulation results using the DIAGCCOS.PAS
600 program to highlight the effect of modifying the angle θ_2 on the shape of the elevation
601 directivity characteristic. In the first stage, the angle θ_1 is fixed at the maximum value of
602 70° . For a comprehensive analysis, both CAD representation in rectangular coordinates
603 and in polar coordinates were utilized.

604 In rectangular coordinates, the variation of the resultant electric field for each angle
605 of the measurement direction θ_p (in degree) is represented, normalized to its maximum
606 value $En(\theta_p) = E_\rho(\theta, \theta_p, \gamma, \rho)/Emax$ in percents, where E_ρ is given by (39) and the values
607 for ρ, θ and γ are determined using the program ANCSOCO4.PAS. In this
608 representation, the blue curve depicts the variation of the resultant electric field
609 normalized to the maximum value, the red curve represents the ideal $cosec^2 \cdot cos$ curve,
610 and the smaller-scale curves at the bottom, each with different colors, represent the
611 synthetic contribution to the resultant field for each section in the vertical plane with step
612 Δz in the horizontal plane, thus providing information on the possibility of modification
613 for the surfaces that could be eliminated for reflector surface optimization.

614 In figure 12.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and
615 $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$. A constant but small deviation from the ideal $cosec^2 \cdot cos$ curve (represented in
616 red) is observed. It closely approximates the ideal curve with a phase shift of 2° . It
617 represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with
618 high-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 12.b, the simulation result is presented when
619 $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates to obtain a dependence of
620 height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). It is easy to observe the reduced level of the lobe near
621 the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).
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Figure 12.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$

Figure 12.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$

In polar coordinates, the representation of vectors $En(\theta_p) = E_p(\theta, \theta_p, \gamma, \rho) / E_{max}$ (in percents) as a function of θ_p has been made. By projecting onto the horizontal axis, the normalized distance (Dn) in percent is obtained, while on the vertical axis, the normalized height (Hn) in percent is obtained, both at the same scale (in the presented cases, the scale is unitary). The result is a simulation of the electric field distribution in distance and height (without considering the curvature of the Earth). The resultant vectors $En(\theta_p) = E_p(\theta, \theta_p, \gamma, \rho) / E_{max}$ (in percents) for each direction θ_p are depicted in blue, while the white line represents the approximation of the directivity characteristic contour.

In the second stage of the analysis, using the DIAGCCOS.PAS program, the angle θ_1 is modified to the value of 60° to highlight the effect on the elevation directivity characteristic in correlation with the same values of the angle θ_2 from the first stage. The simulation results in the second stage are presented in figures 17-21.

In figure 13.a, the simulation result is presented when $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$. A good approximation to the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p . A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction is observed. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with medium-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 13.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). It is easy to observe the reduced level of the lobe near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 13.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$

Figure 13.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$

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In figure 14.a, the simulation result is presented when $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3.5^\circ$. A deviation, smaller than that in the case of $\theta_2=5^\circ$, but constant from the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p . It closely approximates the ideal curve with a phase shift of 1° . A reduction in the maximum radiation direction angle and a slight narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane are observed. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with medium and low-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 14.b, the simulation result is presented when $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and 3.5° , with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). It is easy to observe the reduced level of the lobe near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 14.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3.5^\circ$

Figure 14.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3.5^\circ$

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In figure 15.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3^\circ$. A good approximation to the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p (compared to the case of $\theta_2 = 3.5^\circ$). A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction and a narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane are observed. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with low-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 15.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). It is easy to observe a slight increase in the level of the lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 15.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$

Figure 15.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$

distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$ (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$

In figure 16.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 2.5^\circ$. A good approximation to the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p (compared to the case of $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$). A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction and a narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane are observed. Compared to the case of $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$, there is a slight decrease in the intensity of the electric field for large $\theta_p \in [15; 50]^\circ$. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with low-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 16.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 2.5^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (H_n) versus distance (D_n). It is easy to observe a slight decrease in the level of the lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 16.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 2.5^\circ$

Figure 16.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 2.5^\circ$

In figure 17.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$. A constant but small deviation from the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed. It closely approximates the ideal curve with a phase shift of 2° . Compared to the case of $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$, there is an increase in the dead cone angle, a slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field from lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone), and a narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with medium-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 17.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (H_n) versus distance (D_n). Compared to the case of $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$, there is an increase in the dead cone angle, a slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field from lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 17.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$

Figure 17.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height vs. distance) for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$

In figure 18.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$. A very good approximation to the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p (compared to the case of $\theta_2 = 5^\circ$). A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction and a narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane are observed. Compared to the case of $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$, there is an increase in the dead cone angle, a slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field from lobes near the dead cone. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with medium-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 18.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (H_n) versus distance (D_n). It is easy to observe a slight increase in the level of the lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone) and a small decrease in the width of the characteristic. Compared to the case of $\theta_1 = 70^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$, there is an increase in the dead cone angle, a slight increase in the intensity of the normalized electric field in the radiation zone between lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 18.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$

Figure 18.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$

In figure 19.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3.5^\circ$. A slight but constant deviation from the ideal curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p (compared to the case of $\theta_2 = 4^\circ$). A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction and a narrowing

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of the characteristic in the vertical plane are observed. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with medium and low-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 19.b, simulation results are presented when $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3.5^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). It is easy to observe a slight decrease in the level, but with the maintenance of the shape for the lobes near the limit value of the angle (dead cone) compared to the case of $\theta_2=4^\circ$.

In figure 20.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3^\circ$. A good approximation to the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p (compared to the case of $\theta_2=3.5^\circ$). A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction and a narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane are observed. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with low-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 20.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). Compared to the case of $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3^\circ$, there is an increase in the dead cone angle, a slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field in the radiation zone between lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 19.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3.5^\circ$

Figure 19.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3.5^\circ$

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Figure 20.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$

Figure 20.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$

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In figure 21.a, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=2.5^\circ$. A good approximation to the ideal $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ curve (represented in red) is observed for angles θ_p between 4° and 7.5° , as well as for large θ_p (compared to the case of $\theta_2=3^\circ$). Compared to the case of $\theta_2 = 3^\circ$, there is a slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field for large θ_p (θ_p in the range $[15;50]^\circ$). A reduction in the angle of maximum radiation direction is observed. It represents a suitable directivity characteristic for radars that detect and track targets with low-altitude flight ceilings. In figure 21.b, the simulation result is presented for the case where $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=2.5^\circ$, with representation in polar coordinates of the vectors to obtain a dependence of height (Hn) versus distance (Dn). It is easy to observe a slight decrease in the level of the lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone). Compared to the case of $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and $\theta_2=2.5^\circ$, there is an increase in the dead cone angle, a slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field in the radiation zone between lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone).

Figure 21.a. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, as a function of the elevation angle θ_p for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=2.5^\circ$

Figure 21.b. The normalized electrical field distribution in elevation, in polar coordinates (height versus distance) for $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 2.5^\circ$

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Analysing the simulation results, it can be observed that if θ_1 remains set at its maximum value of 70° and the value of the angle θ_2 is modified (from 5° to 2.5°), the following effects are obtained:

- The angle of maximum radiation direction decreases proportionally with the decrease in the angle θ_2 . This change for the angle of maximum radiation direction results in obtaining directivity characteristics suitable for detecting and tracking targets flying at high altitude (for large θ_2) and at medium altitude (for θ_2 between 4° and 3.5°). The characteristic for $\theta_2=3.5^\circ$ can also be used for medium altitude) and at low altitude (for θ_2 between 3° and 2.5°).
- The shape of the directivity characteristic in elevation approaches more closely to the ideal shape simultaneously with the decrease in the values of the angle θ_2 . A slight narrowing of the characteristic in the vertical plane is also observed.
- Variation in the amplitude and phase of the lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone - the area between the antenna rotation axis and the angle θ_1 , where there is no radiation). Decreasing the angle θ_2 results in the proximity of the level of these lobes to the ideal level curve.
- In the situation where the angle θ_1 is reduced to the value of 60° and the value of the angle θ_2 is modified (from 5° to 2.5° - for the same values used in the simulation where $\theta_1=70^\circ$), the following effects are obtained:

783 - A slight decrease in the intensity of the normalized electric field in the radiation
784 zone between lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone) for angles θ_2 less
785 than 3° and an increase in the intensity of the normalized electric field in the radiation
786 zone between lobes near the limit value of the angle θ_1 (dead cone) for angles θ_2 of [4;
787 5°].

788 Based on the simulations performed, depending on the flight altitude of the targets
789 to be detected and tracked, the following optimal characteristics can be considered:

- 790 - Optimal characteristics for low altitude is obtained with $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=2.5^\circ$.
- 791 - Optimal characteristics for medium altitude is obtained with: $\theta_1=60^\circ$ and $\theta_2=3.5^\circ$.
- 792 - Optimal characteristics for high altitude is obtained with: $\theta_1=70^\circ$ and $\theta_2=5^\circ$.

793 4. Conclusion and Future Work

794 Adapting the elevation directivity characteristic of cosec^2 according to the
795 application needs or radar type, using modified versions of the cosec^2 directivity pattern
796 through studied and experimented variants, is highly beneficial for optimizing
797 subsequent signal processing after reception.

798 There are many options for modifying and optimizing the cosec^2 directivity
799 characteristic. These variations can be achieved with reflector antennas designed
800 appropriately, or with phased array antennas, which are much more expensive and
801 harder to calibrate and maintain.

802 Choosing an elevation directive characteristic of the type $\text{cosec}^2 \cdot \cos$ offers the
803 advantage of a better experimental approximation compared to the theoretical
804 cosec^2 characteristic and a better distribution of radiated power by reducing the
805 secondary lobe in elevation near the maximum elevation angle.

806 This reduction of sidelobe power in the elevation directivity characteristic,
807 particularly for airborne radars, eliminates unwanted effects in signal processing caused
808 by clutter (ground or water surface reflections), providing the ability to track targets
809 without positional losses (if the target is within the clutter zone, it's practically
810 challenging to observe).

811 This type of directive characteristic is useful for radar systems mounted on aircraft
812 as well as for radars used for air surveillance, especially those with wavelengths in the
813 range [1;10] cm. It is also highly suitable for military and civilian radar systems designed
814 for drone detection and tracking, operating at frequencies up to 28 GHz, where
815 azimuthal angular resolution and antenna directivity are of critical importance.
816 Moreover, it proves useful in 5G communication systems, particularly when a constant
817 received power across the antenna radiation pattern is required.

818 Using a primary source with a \cos^4 specific directivity pattern to generate the
819 curve in the symmetry plane results in a decreased vertical dimension of the reflector
820 when compared to employing a \cos^2 different directivity pattern for the primary
821 radiator, under identical angle values $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \theta_1, \theta_2$.

822 Selecting the optimal variant of the reflector with elevation directivity characteristic
823 requires a large volume of simulations with fine variations in the values of reflective
824 angles for the same incident angles, in accordance with the requirements for the radar. It
825 suppose that are known all the performances imposed for the directivity characteristic in
826 azimuth, including the angular resolution at -3dB, the levels of the secondary lobes, the
827 front-back ratio (i.e. the ration between the main lobe power and the back one) and the
828 specificity of the target that needs to be detected (maximum and minimum altitude,
829 target RCS, speed, etc.)

830 As future work, if sufficient funding will be available, we intend to implement
831 physically the antenna, measure its performances and compare them with the theoretical
832 and experimental findings.

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